

Date of analysis:

2022-04-07 (unaged)

2022-05-04 (aged)

Analyst: Kaj Thuresson, Helena Berg**Datum:** 2022-09-04**Dnr:** 2021-3125**Fyndnr.****Löpnr:****Författare:** Helena Berg**Handläggare:** Elyse Canosa

X-ray Instrumental Report

Sample Identification CodeRAÄ Dnr 2021-3125 **Object no.** **suffix****Sample(s)****Object(s):** Mock-ups of painting**Material:** oil paint on Canvas and Melinex**Thickness:**

Purpose

Technical photography is used to visualize the crack formations at, and below, the surface for two mock-ups of Richard Berghs painting *Konstnärsförbundets styrelse* (Nationalmuseum) in order to sort out which pigments might generate cracks.

Instrument Parameters EG&G Torrex 150D X-ray cabinet; Waltham, Massachusetts, U.S.A. GE Eresco 42MF4 portable X-ray unit; Fairfield, Connecticut, U.S.A.

With 33X18 cm or 46X38 cm IPC2 phosphor imaging plate; Fairfield, Connecticut, U.S.A.

(See images: → Imaging plate in plastic cassette, → Imaging plate without cassette)**Software** GE Rhythm Review, Boston; Fairfield, Connecticut, U.S.A. Gnu Image manipulation Program (GIMP); <http://gimp.org>

Digital editing

Includes cropping, brightness/contrast adjustment, "Weld filter", gradient filter and others.

See next page:

Riksantikvarieämbetet

Artillerigatan 33

Box 1114

621 22 Visby

Tel 08-5191 8000**E-post** riksant@raa.se**Hemsida** www.raa.se**Org.nr** 202100-1090**Plusgiro** 59994-4**Bankgiro** 5052-3620

Gradient:

A self-created filter where a gradient (white or black on one side and transparent at the end of the other) is overlaid to remove the heel effect on the image.

Crop:

To remove the parts of the image where no relevant information is found.

Weld:

A built in filter of the Rhythm Review program, designed for quick weld inspection Enhances the contrast between all pixels. Caution: Also enhances anomalies.

Brightness/contrast:

Adjusting the brightness and/or contrast of the image to enhance details.

Frame:

Excluding parts of the image by blackening parts that are not deemed interesting for the investigation or result, like background or equipment.

File name: Canvas aged 220407.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Canvas aged 220504.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Melinex1 unaged 220407.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Canvas aged 220407 filter.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Canvas aged 220504 filter.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Melinex1 unaged 220407 filter.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Melinex1 aged 220504.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing:

File name: Melinex1 aged 220504 filter.tiff

Energy used: 50 keV Current: 5.5 mA Exposure time: 10 s

Distance to object: cm Imaging Plate: 33x48 46x38

Digital editing: